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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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INTERACTIVE APPROACHES TO DEVELOPING EFL LEARNERS' LISTENING SKILLS

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Abstract: This article examines the efficacy of authentic and textbook-based listening resources in enhancing EFL learners' listening comprehension. The study compares student performance, motivation, and perceptions when exposed to authentic audio sources versus standardized textbook recordings. The results indicate that authentic materials enhance listening comprehension and motivation; however, textbook resources remain effective for controlled practice.

Key words: authentic materials, textbook listening, EFL, motivation, comprehension.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqola EFL o'quvchilarining tinglab tushunish ko'nikmalarini rivojlantirishda autentik va darslik asosidagi tinglash materiallarining samaradorligini taqqoslaydi. Tadqiqotda o'quvchilarning natijalari, motivatsiyasi va qarashlari autentik audio manbalar hamda standart darslik yozuvlari asosida tahlil qilinadi. Natijalar autentik materiallar tinglab tushunish va motivatsiyani oshirishda samaraliroq ekanini ko'rsatadi, biroq darslik materiallari tuzilgan mashg'ulotlar uchun foydali bo'lib qolmoqda.

Kalit so'zlar: autentik materiallar, darslik asosidagi tinglash, EFL, motivatsiya, tushunish.

Аннотация: В статье сравнивается эффективность аутентичных и учебных материалов при обучении аудированию студентов EFL. В исследовании анализируются результаты, мотивация и восприятие обучающихся при использовании аутентичных аудиоисточников и стандартных записей из учебников. Результаты показывают, что аутентичные материалы повышают уровень понимания и мотивацию, однако учебные материалы по-прежнему остаются эффективными для структурированных упражнений.

Ключевые слова: аутентичные материалы, аудирование по учебнику, EFL, мотивация, понимание.

INTRODUCTION

Listening comprehension is a crucial component of communicative competence; however, the selection of appropriate instructional materials remains a significant pedagogical challenge. EFL teachers frequently rely on linguistically simplified textbook recordings, whereas authentic resources such as podcasts, radio broadcasts, and interviews provide learners with exposure to real-world language use [3: 97–100]. Textbook materials are designed to ensure pedagogical control through graded vocabulary, clear pronunciation, and predictable organization. Nevertheless, they often lack spontaneity, natural intonation patterns, and cultural richness. Authentic materials, by contrast, reflect real communicative situations and enable learners to adapt to natural speech rates and linguistic variability [8: 467–478]. This study aims to examine the effectiveness of these two types of listening resources in enhancing listening comprehension, increasing learner motivation, and encouraging active participation in EFL classrooms.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study involved thirty intermediate-level EFL learners aged 17–21, enrolled in a private language institute in Samarkand, Uzbekistan. Participants were selected from intact classes and assigned to two groups with comparable English proficiency levels, as determined by institutional placement tests and teacher evaluations.

Group A (n = 15) received instruction using authentic listening materials, including BBC podcasts and selected TED Talk excerpts.

Group B (n = 15) was taught using textbook-based listening materials taken from the Headway Pre-Intermediate and Intermediate Student's Books.

All participants had similar prior exposure to instructional listening tasks but limited experience with extended authentic audio input. This ensured a high degree of homogeneity between the groups, thereby strengthening the internal validity of the study.

The research employed a quasi-experimental comparative design. The independent variable was the type of listening material (authentic vs. textbook-based), while the dependent variables were learners' listening comprehension performance and motivation toward listening activities. Both groups participated in four listening sessions over a two-week period. Each session followed a consistent instructional structure consisting of a pre-listening warm-up involving brief discussion or guiding questions related to the topic, a listening activity featuring exposure to the audio text, and a post-listening task that included a comprehension test and a short reflective commentary.

Group A (Authentic Materials) listened to unscripted audio recordings such as news reports, interviews, and short talks. These materials demonstrated natural speech characteristics, including varied accents, reduced forms, hesitations, and a natural speaking pace. Group B (Textbook Materials) listened to carefully controlled textbook audio specifically designed for pedagogical purposes. These recordings featured clear articulation, graded vocabulary, and a slower speaking rate.

Upon completion of all sessions, learners in both groups completed a motivation questionnaire designed to assess their attitudes toward the listening activities. The following instruments were employed in the study. Listening comprehension tests were administered in each session and consisted of ten multiple-choice items, with one point awarded for each correct answer, yielding a maximum score of 10 points. In addition, a motivation questionnaire based on a five-point Likert scale (1 = extremely low, 5 = very high) was used to measure students' interest, perceived usefulness, and enjoyment of the listening activities.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Teacher observation checklist: classroom observations were conducted systematically using a standardized checklist to document learners' levels of interest, attention, and participation during listening exercises. The checklist also included behavioral variables such as note-taking, task attentiveness, and readiness to participate in follow-up discussions, which provided qualitative support for the quantitative results.

Table 1: Comparison of listening comprehension scores

Group	Mean Score (out of 10)	Standard Deviation
Authentic materials (Group A)	8.7	0.8
Textbook materials (Group B)	7.2	1.0

Table 1 indicates that learners exposed to authentic listening materials achieved higher mean comprehension scores than those who used textbook recordings. The lower standard deviation in Group A suggests more consistent performance, indicating that authentic materials supported comprehension across learners with varying initial proficiency levels.

Table 2: Learner motivation ratings

Group	Mean Motivation Rating (1–5)
Authentic materials (Group A)	4.6
Textbook materials (Group B)	3.9

As shown in Table 2, students in Group A demonstrated significantly higher levels of motivation. Participants reported that authentic materials appeared more relevant and engaging, even though they required greater concentration. The findings of this study demonstrate that the use of authentic listening materials enhances both listening comprehension and learner motivation. Learners who were exposed to real-world audio input performed better than those who relied exclusively on textbook recordings. One possible explanation for this improvement is that authentic materials expose learners to natural speech features such as connected speech patterns, discourse markers, and pragmatic cues. Although such materials may appear challenging at first, sustained exposure enables learners to develop effective top-down and bottom-up listening strategies ^[2:38–41].

The higher motivation ratings reported by learners using authentic materials indicate that perceived relevance and realism play a crucial role in sustaining learner engagement. When students recognize a clear connection between classroom listening activities and real-life communication, their willingness to invest effort increases. This conclusion aligns with theories of motivation in second language acquisition, which emphasize authenticity as a key determinant of learner engagement ^[1:27–35].

Teacher observations further revealed that learners in Group A were more attentive and actively participated in listening tasks, despite occasionally experiencing difficulties. This finding supports the view that appropriately challenging tasks can enhance motivation and promote deeper cognitive processing [3:97–118].

From a pedagogical perspective, these results suggest that while textbook materials provide valuable scaffolding, authentic resources should be systematically integrated into EFL listening instruction to better prepare learners for real-world communication. Consequently, EFL teachers are encouraged to gradually incorporate authentic listening materials alongside textbook resources. Such an approach not only improves listening proficiency but also increases learner motivation and confidence, ultimately preparing students for effective communication beyond the classroom.

CONCLUSION

This study examined the impact of authentic versus textbook-based listening materials on EFL learners' listening comprehension and motivation. The findings indicate that learners exposed to authentic audio input demonstrated higher levels of comprehension and motivation compared to those who relied solely on textbook recordings. Although students initially found authentic materials more challenging, continued exposure enabled them to adapt to natural speech patterns and significantly improve their ability to understand real-life spoken English. These findings underscore the importance of balancing pedagogical support with authenticity in listening instruction. This study also highlights the need for further research into the long-term effects of authentic listening exposure, its impact on learners across different proficiency levels, and its integration with strategy instruction and social-emotional learning frameworks.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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